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Speech enhancement approach based on improved minima controlled recursive averaging using continuous spectral minimum tracking

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Abstract. The accuracy of noise estimation determines the speech enhancement effect. In order to improve the accuracy of noise estimation, track non-stationary noise timely, a speech enhancement approach based on improved minima controlled recursive averaging using continuous spectral minimum tracking is proposed in this paper. The proposed algorithm improves the noise estimation by continuously smoothing each frequency of the noisy speech power spectrum and then searching the minimum value in the sub-window to achieve the purpose of reducing the frame delay. The experimental results show that proposed algorithm can more accurately estimate the noise spectrum and improve the speech quality.

Keywords: Noise estimation, Improved minima controlled recursive averaging, Minimum tracking, Speech enhancement

1 Introduction

In single channel speech enhancement algorithms, the spectral-subtractive algorithm is historically one of the first algorithms proposed for noise reduction. It is based on a simple principle. Assuming additive noise, one can obtain an estimate of the clean signal spectrum by subtracting an estimate of the noise spectrum from the noisy speech spectrum. Therefore, it is very important to estimate noise spectrum accurately. If the noise estimate is too low, annoying residual noise will be audible, while if the noise estimate is too high, speech will be distorted resulting possibly in intelligibility loss. In order to accurately estimate the noise, people make a lot of efforts, for examples, Martin [1] proposed a method to estimate the noise spectrum based on tracking the minimum of the noisy speech over a finite window. As the minimum is typically smaller than the mean, unbiased estimates of noise spectrum were computed by introducing a bias factor based on the statistics of the minimum estimates. The time-recursive averaging algorithm exploit the observation that the noise signal typically has a non-uniform effect on the spectrum of speech, in that some regions of the spectrum are affected by noise more than others. The noise spectrum is estimated as a weighted average of the past noise estimates and the present noisy speech spectrum. The weights change adaptively depending either on the effective SNR of each fre-

quency bin or on the speech-presence probability [2]. Cohen proposed a minima controlled recursive algorithm(MCRA) [3] which updates the noise estimate by tracking the noise-only regions of the noisy speech spectrum. These regions are found by comparing the ratio of the noisy speech to the local minimum against a threshold. The noise estimate, however, lags by at most twice that window length when the noise spectrum increases abruptly. Rather than using the MS approach for tracking the minima, the authors [4] used the continuous spectral minima-tracking method. Unlike the MS approach, this method tracks the minima continuously and is not constrained within a finite window. More precisely, the fixed threshold δ was replaced by frequency-dependent threshold. In the improved MCRA(IMCRA) approach [5], a different method was used to track the noise-only regions of the spectrum based on the estimated speech-presence probability. This probability, however, is also controlled by the minima, and therefore the algorithm incurs roughly the same delay as the MCRA algorithm for increasing noise levels. An improved IMCRA algorithm for non-stationary noise estimation, the speech present probability is calculated in three iterative to determine the length of search window, and noise estimation is limited or compensated with safety mechanism [6]. Both minima tracking methods of forward searching and backward searching are utilized together based on IMCRA algorithm in [7]. combines MS algorithm, and the recursive averaging parameter is improved in [8] based on IMCRA noise spectrum estimation algorithm, at the same time, a recursive way is used to improve the minimum value of smoothing power spectrum. An improved minimum search method is proposed in [9]. It is consisted of two parallel searches with different window lengths. The results of the minimum search are determined by the ones of the two parallel searches and the binary decision about speech presence based on the noise classification.

A speech enhancement approach based on IMCRA using continuous spectral minimum tracking is presented in this paper after combining speech existence probability estimation of IMCRA and the tracking method in [10]. Experiments show that comparing the IMCRA, the proposed algorithm have an improvement in segmental SNR and mean opinion score.

2 Proposed Noise-estimation Algorithm

It is assumed that clean speech and noise are statistically independent and zero mean, that means the power spectrum of noisy speech is the sum of power spectrum of clean speech and noise

$$|Y(k,l)|^2 = |X(k,l)|^2 + |D(k,l)|^2 \quad (1)$$

Among them, $|Y(k,l)|^2$, $|X(k,l)|^2$ and $|D(k,l)|^2$ represent power spectrum of noisy speech, clean speech and noise respectively. l indicates the frame index, and k indicates the frequency bin index. Given two hypotheses

$$\begin{aligned} H_0(k, l) : Y(k, l) &= D(k, l) \\ H_1(k, l) : Y(k, l) &= X(k, l) + D(k, l) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Among them, $H_0(k, l)$ and $H_1(k, l)$ indicate respectively speech absence and presence in the k th frequency bin of the l th frame. In IMCRA algorithm, speech and noise of the short-time Fourier transform of the probability density function is assumed to be Gaussian [11] and conditional speech probability can be expressed as

$$p(k, l) = P(H_1(k, l) | \gamma(k, l)) = \left\{ 1 + \frac{q(k, l)}{1 - q(k, l)} (1 + \xi(k, l)) \exp(v(k, l)) \right\}^{-1} \quad (3)$$

Among them, $q(k, l) = p(H_0(k, l))$ the prior probability of speech do not exist, and $v = \gamma\tilde{\xi}/(1 + \tilde{\xi})$, λ and $\tilde{\xi}$ representing a posteriori and a priori SNR. IMCRA noise update algorithm is similar to MCRA algorithms, probabilistic available voice using the above conditions exist

$$\hat{\lambda}_d(k, l + 1) = \tilde{\alpha}_d(k, l) \hat{\lambda}_d(k, l) + [1 - \tilde{\alpha}_d(k, l)] |Y(k, l)|^2 \quad (4)$$

Among them, $\tilde{\alpha}_d(k, l) = \alpha_d + (1 - \alpha_d)p(k, l)$. The speech presence probability also modifies the spectral estimate of the clean speech, and therefore is generally biased toward higher values to avoid speech distortions in speech enhancement applications. A bias compensation factor is included in

$$\hat{\lambda}_d(k, l + 1) = \beta \cdot \hat{\lambda}_d(k, l + 1) \quad (5)$$

In order to calculate the condition probability IMCRA algorithm, two iterations of smoothing and minimum tracking are required, smoothing in time is performed by a first order recursive averaging

$$S(k, l) = \alpha_s S(k, l - 1) + (1 - \alpha_s) S_f(k, l) \quad (6)$$

Among them,

$$S_f(k, l) = \sum_{i=-\omega}^{\omega} b(i) |Y(k - i, l)|^2 \quad (7)$$

$b(i)$ is the normalized Hamming window. Smoothing parameter α_s is a constant. The nonlinear rule used for estimating the noise spectrum based on tracking the minimum of the noisy speech power spectrum in each frequency bin is as follows

If $S_{\min}(\lambda - 1, k) < S(\lambda, k)$

$$S_{\min}(\lambda, k) = \delta S(\lambda - 1, k) + \frac{1 - \delta}{1 - \chi} (S(\lambda, k) - \chi S(\lambda - 1, k))$$

else

$$S_{\min}(\lambda, k) = S(\lambda, k)$$

end (8)

Where $S_{\min}(\lambda, k)$ is the local minimum of the noisy speech power spectrum, δ and χ are constants which are determined experimentally. Here $\chi = 0.96$, $\delta = 0.998$. The preceding rule uses a “look-ahead” factor δ in the minimum tracking which can be adjusted if needed to vary the adaptation time of the algorithm. The typical adaptation time using the values mentioned previously is 0.2-0.4s [2].

After getting the local minimum, two ratios are defined by

$$\gamma_{\min}(k, l) \triangleq \frac{|Y(k, l)|^2}{B_{\min} P_{\min}(k, l)} \quad (9)$$

$$\zeta(k, l) \triangleq \frac{S(k, l)}{B_{\min} P_{\min}(k, l)} \quad (10)$$

Based on first-order recursive smoothing and minimum search results, the speech makes a bold decision.

$$I(k, l) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \gamma_{\min}(k, l) < \gamma_0 \text{ and } \zeta(k, l) < \zeta_0 \text{ speech is absent} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \text{ speech is present} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

When the noisy speech power spectra and local minimum ratio is greater than a threshold value, speech is present. Otherwise, speech is absent. The second iteration of smoothing includes only the power spectral components, which have been identified as containing primarily noise. Setting the initial frame by $S(k, 0) = S_f(k, 0)$. Then, for $l > 0$ the smoothing in frequency, employing the above voice activity detector, is obtained by

$$\tilde{S}_f(k, l) = \begin{cases} \frac{\sum_{i=-\omega}^{\omega} b(i) I(k-i, l) |Y(k-i, l)|^2}{\sum_{i=-\omega}^{\omega} b(i) I(k-i, l)}, & \text{if } \sum_{i=-\omega}^{\omega} I(k-i, l) \neq 0 \\ \tilde{S}_f(k, l-1), & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Second time-domain smoothing is the same as before, using a first order recursive averaging

$$\tilde{S}(k, l) = \alpha_s \tilde{S}(k, l-1) + (1 - \alpha_s) \tilde{S}_f(k, l) \quad (13)$$

Tracking minimum in the second recursive smoothing results

$$\text{If } \tilde{S}_{\min}(\lambda - 1, k) < \tilde{S}(\lambda, k)$$

$$\tilde{S}_{\min}(\lambda, k) = \delta \tilde{S}(\lambda - 1, k) + \frac{1 - \delta}{1 - \chi} (\tilde{S}(\lambda, k) - \chi \tilde{S}(\lambda - 1, k))$$

else

$$\tilde{S}_{\min}(\lambda, k) = \tilde{S}(\lambda, k)$$

end

(14)

Let $\tilde{\gamma}_{\min}(k, l)$ and $\tilde{\zeta}(k, l)$ be defined by

$$\tilde{\gamma}_{\min}(k, l) \stackrel{\Delta}{=} \frac{|Y(k, l)|^2}{B_{\min} \tilde{S}_{\min}(k, l)} \quad (15)$$

$$\tilde{\zeta}(k, l) \stackrel{\Delta}{=} \frac{S(k, l)}{B_{\min} \tilde{S}_{\min}(k, l)} \quad (16)$$

Based on the result, and threshold γ_1 and ζ_0 , estimation of the prior probability of speech absence can be obtained

$$\tilde{q}(k, l) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{when } \tilde{\gamma}_{\min}(k, l) < 1 \text{ and } \tilde{\zeta}(k, l) < \zeta_0 \\ \frac{(\gamma_1 - \tilde{\gamma}_{\min}(k, l))}{(\gamma_1 - 1)}, & \text{when } 1 < \tilde{\gamma}_{\min}(k, l) < \gamma_1 \text{ and } \tilde{\zeta}(k, l) < \zeta_0 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

In order to get the condition probability, a posteriori SNR γ and a priori SNR ξ are needed to calculate, which defined separately for

$$\gamma(k, l) \stackrel{\Delta}{=} \frac{|Y(k, l)|^2}{\lambda_d(k, l)} \quad (18)$$

$$\xi(k, l) \stackrel{\Delta}{=} \frac{\lambda_x(k, l)}{\lambda_d(k, l)} \quad (19)$$

Among them, the posteriori SNR can be estimated according to the results, the a priori SNR is estimated by

$$\hat{\xi}(k, l) = \alpha \mathbf{G}_{H_1}^2(k, l - 1) \gamma(k, l - 1) + (1 - \alpha) \max\{\gamma(k, l) - 1, 0\} \quad (20)$$

Where α is a weighting factor that controls the trade-off between noise reduction and speech distortion [12], and $\mathbf{G}_{H_1}(k, l)$ is the spectral gain function of the Log-Spectral Amplitude(LSA) estimator when speech is surely present [13].

After getting $\tilde{q}(k,l)$, $\tilde{\xi}(k,l)$ and $\gamma(k,l)$, conditional probability of speech presence can be computed using (3), further the time and frequency dependent psd smoothing parameter can be obtained. Finally updating estimation of noise using (4). Fig. 1 shows the proposed algorithm.

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Let  $j=0$ .      %  $j$  is a counter for frames within a sub-window.
For all time frames  $l$ 
  For all frequency bins  $k$ 
    Compute the a posteriori SNR  $\gamma(k,l)$  and the a prior SNR  $\hat{\xi}(k,l)$ .
    Compute the first iteration of smoothed power spectrum  $S(k,l)$ , and update its running minimum using Eq. (8).
    Compute the indicator function  $I(k,l)$  for the voice activity detection.
    Compute the second iteration of smoothed power spectrum  $\tilde{S}(k,l)$ , and update its running minimum using Eq. (14).
    Compute the a priori speech absence probability  $\hat{q}(k,l)$ , the speech presence probability  $p(k,l)$ , and the time-varying smoothing parameter  $\tilde{\alpha}_d(k,l)$ .
    Update the noise spectrum estimate  $\hat{\lambda}_d(k,l+1)$ .
  Let  $j = j + 1$ 
If  $j=V$ 
  For all frequency bins  $k$ 
    Store  $S_{\min}(k)$ , set  $S_{\min}(k,l)$  to the minimum of the last  $U$  stored values of  $S_{\min}(k)$ , and let  $S_{\min}(k) = S(k,l)$ .
    Store  $\tilde{S}_{\min}(k)$ , set  $\tilde{S}_{\min}(k,l)$  to the minimum of the last  $U$  stored values of  $\tilde{S}_{\min}(k)$ , and let  $\tilde{S}_{\min}(k) = \tilde{S}(k,l)$ .
  Let  $j = 0$ .

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Fig. 1. Proposed noise estimation algorithm.

3 Performance Evaluation

The utterances, half from male speakers and half from female speakers, are taken from the TIMIT database. The speech signal is sampled at 16 kHz and degraded by the various noise types with segmental SNR's in the range [-5,5] dB. The noise signals used in our evaluation are taken from the Noisex92 database [14]. They include babble, factory, white, street noise, and cafeteria. The spectral analysis is implemented with Hamming windows of 320 samples length and 160 samples frame update step. Other values of parameters used in the implementation of proposed algorithm are showed in table 1.

Table 1. Value of parameters used in the implementation of proposed algorithm

$\omega = 1$	$\alpha_s = 0.9$	$U = 8$	$V = 15$
$D = 120$	$B_{\min} = 1.66$	$\gamma_0 = 4.6$	$\gamma_1 = 3$
$\zeta_0 = 1.67$	$\alpha = 0.92$	$\alpha_d = 0.85$	$\beta = 1.47$
$\delta = 0.998$	$\chi = 0.96$	b: Hanning window	

Simulation experiment shows the enhancement effect of IMCRA and proposed algorithm about three different types and different SNR of noise.

Fig.2 shows the result of two algorithms about noisy speech added 0dB babble noise, in which top is the original noisy speech waveform, center is the enhanced speech waveform using the IMCRA noise estimate, bottom is the enhanced speech waveform using proposed algorithm. Fig.3 shows the spectrogram using IMCRA. Fig.4 shows the spectrogram using proposed algorithm. From the figures it can be seen that the enhancement effect of proposed algorithm is better than IMCRA.

Fig. 2. Original noisy speech waveform(top) and enhanced speech waveform using the two algorithms.

Fig. 3. Spectrogram using the IMCRA

Eight utterances are chosen which degraded by babble, cafeteria and street noise, with segmental SNR's in the range $[-5,5]$ dB, and then enhance them by IMCRA and the proposed algorithm. Enhancement effect is evaluated objectively by output segmental SNR(SegSNR) [15]. Table 2. shows the output SegSNR of proposed algorithm has increased value than the output SegSNR of IMCRA. Moreover, as the decline of input SegSNR, enhancement effect is more obvious. From the waveform, spectrogram and increased segmental SNR, the consistent results can be concluded that proposed algorithm is better than IMCRA.

Fig. 4. Spectrogram used proposed algorithm

Table 2. SegSNR of two algorithms for different types of noisy speech

Type		babble			cafeteria			street noise		
Input SegSNR		-5	0	5	-5	0	5	-5	0	5
Output SegSNR	IMCRA [5]	7.94	7.56	6.92	7.29	7.04	6.50	6.98	6.88	6.67
	Proposed algorithm	8.40	7.88	7.17	7.64	7.30	6.77	7.57	7.51	7.35

Speech enhancement effect is also valued by informal tests of subjective evaluation [15]. There are 11 people (7 men and 4 women, aged 21-26 years) participating the tests. All these people are not covered in this paper work and also did not participate in mean opinion score tests experience. Table 3. shows the results of mean opinion score tests. It can be seen that mean opinion score of proposed algorithm is higher than that of IMCRA.

Table 3. Mean opinion score of different types of voice

Input SNR	Original speech	IMCRA [5]	Proposed algorithm
-5	1.27	2.06	2.55
0	1.64	2.97	3.11
5	2.71	3.31	3.58

4 Conclusion

This paper presents a speech enhancement approach based on IMCRA using continuous spectral minimum. The algorithm uses both continuous spectral minimum and split-window when tracking the minimum of smooth power spectrum, such that the delay of noise estimation can be reduced effectively. Compared with IMCRA, proposed algorithm improves the accuracy of background noise estimation and gets better noise removal effect. Simulation results show that, the estimation effect of the algorithms presented in this paper is better than IMCRA for some typical noisy speech. The SegSNR of proposed algorithm is higher about 0.2~0.8 dB than the original algorithm in low SNR condition. Informal subjective listening tests also show that mean opinion score of proposed algorithm is higher than IMCRA.

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